

FATIGUE OF GLASS FIBERS REINFORCED POLYAMIDES: MEAN STRESS EFFECTS AS A FUNCTION OF GLASS FIBERS ORIENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Anisotropy has a major impact on fatigue properties of short glass fibres reinforced polyamides. The impact of load ratio on fatigue properties of these materials has been studied using jointly mechanical testing; digital image correlation and infrared thermography at a frequency of 3Hz. Materials tested contained 30% in weight of glass fibres, at 3 different glass fibres orientation. Haigh diagrams appear quite complex. Lines of constant life appear parallel in a wide range of load ratios, and their shape doesn't correspond to any classical mean stress correction. Material behaviour during fatigue tests also depends tremendously on load ratio. Hysteresis loops, strain accumulation, modulus evolution and self-heating have been followed during fatigue tests. Hysteresis loops appear very sensitive to stress amplitude, while strain accumulation depends highly on mean stress. Specimens submitted to negative load ratios show stronger modulus reduction than others, because of both higher damage level and larger thermal softening. Infrared thermography showed that a strong relationship between the load ratio of fatigue tests and the level of temperature achieved on specimens surface: for negative load ratios, at the same fatigue resistance, stress amplitude, hysteresis loops area and self-heating become more important. Correlations between mechanical values such as strain energy or hysteresis loops areas and fatigue resistance have been tested and are still investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fatigue of short fibres reinforced polyamides can often be the mechanical property that drives the design of moulded parts. Parts shape definition relies either on part testing, either on safety coefficients learnt from the past developments made on parts having similar functions and undergoing similar loadings. Until very recently, no fatigue simulation technology allowed taking into account glass fibre orientation which is nevertheless a first order parameter in fatigue resistance, as is already well known^[1-6].

To develop an integrative simulation technology dedicated to fatigue simulation, a collaborative project, DURAFIP, has been built. It is funded by French administration (FUI, *Fond Unifié Interministériel*). It involves 14 partners, industrial companies and academic partners. Most of them are French. Industrial partners such as Toyota, PSA, Trelleborg/Vibracoustic, and SOGEFI can be found among them. e-Xstream and Solvay Engineering Plastics also belong to this project.

DigimatTM is commercial software edited by e-Xstream that allows simulations taking into account material anisotropy. First versions of this software were dedicated to static or dynamic computations, and did not allow parts fatigue behaviour evaluation. Recent versions include still partially limited fatigue capabilities that will be developed in the future releases.

Most of the times, fibre reinforced polyamides are used in their glass transition range or above. In these domains, they have a complex mechanical behaviour that makes fatigue computations potentially

difficult. It exhibits strong nonlinearities which can be viscoelastic, or caused by other phenomena (viscoplasticity, damage...). A first consequence of these nonlinearities is the existence of strong hysteresis loops, as illustrated on Figure 1. These hysteresis loops correspond to an energy which is at least partially dissipated into heat. They cause a temperature rise of the material on specimen or parts. This self-heating can reach considerable amounts when the test frequency or maximum stresses are high enough [7]. All the nonlinearities described before can't be taken easily into account in a usual fatigue computation where the material is assumed to be purely elastic.

Figure 1: hysteresis loops during a fatigue test on a 30% glass fibres reinforced PA66 with fibres oriented at 45°, load ratio $R_\sigma = -0.2$, nominal maximum stress 46MPa. Each loop corresponds to one specific cycle during a fatigue test.

Fatigue behaviour of reinforced materials depends also on the balance between stress amplitude σ_a and mean stress σ_m as shown on Figure 2 which pictures 2 S-N curves obtained with two different load ratios $R_\sigma = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$ for two different glass fibres orientations. This phenomenon is called the mean stress effect. One of the features that were previously missing in Digimat™ is the ability to perform mean stress corrections, which allow predicting fatigue resistance independently of the balance between σ_a and σ_m . It appears that literature dedicated to short fibres reinforced polyamides is scarce [8] that subject and that no detailed studies about the relationship between glass fibre orientation and mean stress influence have been published so far.

Figure 2: S-N curves obtained on A218V30 with 2 different orientations (longitudinal and transverse) and two different load ratios R_σ

One of Solvay's main tasks in this project is to acquire data on mean stress effects. The target of the experimental work led is first to build a Haigh diagram where lines of constant life are plotted as functions of mean stress and stress amplitude. However, in order to get a good understanding of material behaviour, S-N curves are not the only elements which have been measured. All the

nonlinearities above mentioned have to be quantified in order to evaluate the need to take them into account in a fatigue simulation. As a consequence, secant modulus, strain accumulation, hysteresis loops and temperature rise have been followed during all tests.

Measuring S-N curves in wide range of orientations and load ratios, and quantifying material behaviour accurately should give DURAFIP other partners such as e-Xstream good guidelines for software development, and should allow much better fatigue computations taking into account mean stress effects, material anisotropy, and potentially thermal effects or relevant material nonlinearities.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Specimens molding and machining

Gating system and dimensions of the plaques used in this study are defined on

Figure 3. Plaque thickness is 3mm. The line gate and the important flow length ensure a high level of glass fibres orientation and a very homogenous orientation along the plaque. Specimens are machined along plaques' symmetry axis at the following angles: 0°, 45° and 90°. Useful zones of all the specimens are cut in a limited portion of the plaque: the minimum distance with the line gate is 100mm. The minimum distance with the opposite end is also 100mm. This allows a maximum homogeneity of the specimens. Specimen geometry is defined on Figure 4. The specimens have a parallel length of 20mm and a quite important width of 14mm. With a thickness of 3mm they have a quite good resistance to buckling that is very helpful for measurements made with negative load ratios.

Figure 3: plaques used in DURAFIP project

Figure 4: specimen shape and main dimensions

2.2 Specimens microstructure

Glass fibre orientation and length have been measured prior to any mechanical measurements. Glass fibre length has been measured with a standard technique. Average length is close to 250 μ m. Orientation has been measured thanks to high resolution computed microtomography. Experiments and reconstruction of the pictures have been made in European Synchrotron Radiation Facility, in Grenoble on line ID19. Pictures have then been treated and orientation tensors \mathbf{a}_2 and \mathbf{a}_4 computed. Orientation tensors are the most common way to compute fibres orientation. They are computed from fibres individual Euler angles following the definitions in Figure 5. Inside tensor \mathbf{a}_2 , component a_{11} corresponds to the fraction of fibres oriented along the flow direction. a_{33} corresponds to out of plane

component of orientation, and remains limited to very small values. This means that fibres are distributed in a plane. a_{12} component, in the case of a plane orientation roughly indicates if the fibres are aligned with the main directions or not. Figure 6 shows components a_{11} and a_{12} of the second order orientation tensor in two different locations A and B. Both have been taken on plaque symmetry axis A has been chosen at a distance of 100mm of the gate. B is measured at 100mm of plaque end. Both locations are located on the extremities of the area where specimen are cut. Each location has been measured twice on two different plaques. The figure shows that plaque homogeneity is very good. Moreover, component a_{12} shows something quite unusual. For all specimens, it takes important values in the centre. This part of the total thickness is the core of the specimen, where orientation is supposed to be transverse. It is not exactly the case, because a_{11} should be low, which is true, and a_{12} should stay close to zero. Results measured mean that the core is tilted at an angle close to 70° .

Figure 5: definition of Euler angles θ , ϕ , and of orientation tensor a_2

Figure 6: dependence of orientation tensor components on specimen location, and variability of microstructure on two different plaques

2.3 Mechanical testing and self-heating characterization

Mechanical characterisations have been made on two MTS servohydraulic machines, MTS 319.02 and MTS 370.10 equipped with extensometers when Digital Image Correlation is not used to measure strain. Both technologies have been crosschecked and give similar results. Temperature and relative hygrometry are controlled on each machine with Weiss climatic chambers. Strain fields on specimen surface are monitored with two cameras, and data are treated with VIC3D software. Temperature fields are measured with an infrared camera FLIR X6540SC. Specimens are observed inside the climatic chamber through a CaF_2 window having a transmission coefficient measured at 0.98 thanks to a reference black body. Self-heating is measured by comparing the mean temperature of a not solicited reference specimen and the maximum temperature observed on the specimen. The tests are not fully filmed. MTS electronics generates a TTL pulse that activates visible cameras, infrared cameras and storage of stress and strain for a whole cycle.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Effect of orientation on S-N curves

Effect of anisotropy induced by the glass fibres orientation on S-N curves has been described elsewhere and is well known. Our results are in full agreement with previous results in the literature.

3.2 Effect of load ratio S-N curves

S-N curves have been measured for three different orientations with the same load ratios. Minimum load ratio R_r was -0.5. It was carefully checked thanks to Digital Image Correlation that no buckling occurs during the tests. Maximum load ratio is 0.7. Results obtained for longitudinal specimens are given on Figure 7. Results obtained on other orientations show similar trends. All the stresses on the S-N curves are nominal stresses and do not take into account local stress concentrations on specimen radius edge

Figure 7: mean stress sensitivity of a polyamide 6.6 reinforced with 30% glass fibres longitudinally oriented at room temperature, 50% relative hygrometry

3.3 Haigh diagram of a 30%w reinforced polyamide 6.6 (TY A218V30)

(a) Longitudinal fibres

(b) Transverse fibres

Figure 8: lines of constant life (10^4 cycles) for longitudinal and transverse specimens machined in a plaque, made of 30% glass fibres reinforced polyamides. Blue dashed lines correspond to a linear mean stress correction and red dashed lines correspond to a parabolic correction

The amount of data measured has allowed building a Haigh diagram. Lines of constant life are drawn as a function of $\sigma_m = \sigma_{max} \cdot (1 + R_\sigma) / 2$ as x axis and $\sigma_a = \sigma_{max} \cdot (1 - R_\sigma) / 2$ as y axis. Figure 8 (a) for longitudinal specimens and (b) for transverse specimens shows lines of constant lives at 10^4 cycles. Results at 45° show an intermediate trend. In first approximation, data might be considered as linear, especially for longitudinal specimens. Nevertheless, at high load ratios, the drop of properties accelerates, which is especially clear for transverse specimens.

Some basic mean stress corrections are also shown on Figure 8: A linear correction in blue and a parabolic correction in red. Both give acceptable results. Nevertheless parabolic correction gives a better fit of data, especially for transverse specimens. Of course, a result obtained on a so limited amount of data (one fibre concentration, one temperature, one relative hygrometry, one frequency) must be considered with much caution and not generalised too quickly. Moreover when tensile stresses corresponding to $R_\sigma = 1$ are computed, it appears that linear correction gives values having more physical meaning than parabolic correction.

When other lines of constant life are considered, some new trends can be observed. It appears that until $R_\sigma = 0,3$ they are parallel rather than converging towards the x axis, as shown on figure 9. For higher load ratios they start to converge. A linear fit on the curves obtained shows that they do not converge towards the same stress on x -axis. This means that usual linear corrections can't be applied with accuracy, and that lines of constant life must be identified independently. Results obtained do not allow a standard Goodman correction with a single UTS. Similarly Gerber corrections can't be applied as such in the parabolic case, because UTS can't be used either.

Figure 9: lines of constant life for longitudinal specimens.

3.4 Some trends on hysteresis loops

Other features of fatigue behaviour help to explain some of the observations made above. Of course, during a fatigue test, secant modulus of the material evolves and a progressive ratcheting can be observed. These two phenomena show a strong dependency on load ratio, but they're not in the focus of this abstract. Two points can be emphasized about hysteresis loops. First, as could be observed on Figure 1, hysteresis loops can evolve during a fatigue test. For high load ratios, whatever the glass fibre orientation, hysteresis loops stabilise very quickly as shown on Figure 10a where hysteresis loop area is shown all along fatigue tests. For the low load ratios, hysteresis loops hardly stabilise at all during all test length, whatever the fatigue resistance, as shown on Figure 10b.

The second point that can be emphasized about hysteresis loops is that they deeply depend on stress amplitude. On Figure 11 is drawn as a function of stress amplitude the hysteresis loop area averaged on the whole fatigue test. Longitudinal specimens at all load ratios follow the same curve. The two other orientations are on a separate ensemble, with more data dispersion.

(a) $R_{\sigma}=0,3$

(b) $R_{\sigma}=-0,5$

Figure 10: hysteresis loops area evolution during fatigue tests as a function of stress and load ratio for longitudinal specimens

Figure 11: average hysteresis loop area as a function of nominal stress amplitude for different glass fibres orientation

3.5 Self-heating as a function of glass fibers orientation

(a) Evolution of maximum temperature on specimen surface as a function of maximum stress (longitudinal specimens, $R_{\sigma} = -0,5$)

(b) Average value of maximum self-heating during fatigue test for different orientations

Figure 12: self-heating during fatigue tests at $R_\sigma = -0.5$

Self-heating of the specimens also appears to depend strongly on load ratio R_σ . Maximum temperature of the specimen can be followed during the tests. Trends similar to those observed on hysteresis loops are observed on self-heating. Temperature is stable only for high load ratios or tests longer than $3 \cdot 10^5$ cycles for negative load ratios. Average maximum temperature for a complete fatigue test can be computed. It is shown on Figure 12 for three different glass fibres orientations and a constant load ratio $R_\sigma = -0.5$ where the maximum self-heating have been observed. 45° and 90° specimens are quite similar. Their self-heating is higher than those observed on 0° specimens. It appears on that graph that the testing frequency, 3Hz was most probably a poor choice, because for negative load ratios it generates a considerable self-heating.

3.6 Self-heating as a function of load ratio

Observations on self-heating can also be made as a function of load ratio R_σ for a fixed glass fibre orientation. Results available are shown on Figure 13. When load ratio decreases, for a given fatigue resistance self-heating gets bigger, especially for tests lasting less than $3 \cdot 10^5$ cycles. For longer fatigue tests self-heating observed tend to converge and become independent of the load ratio applied. The strong self-heating observed for short tests and negative load ratio may have an impact on the Haigh diagrams on Figure 8a and b. The curvature observed on the line of constant life at 10^4 cycles is most probably caused by the temperature rise of the specimens in these specific conditions.

Figure 13: average self-heating during fatigue tests for longitudinal specimens at several load ratios

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Correlations between self-heating and hysteresis loops

The observations made above about self-heating can be related to hysteresis evolution quite easily. An energy balance^[8] made on a specimen follows the equation (1) where the left term \dot{W}_{def} is the rate of strain energy. It corresponds to the hysteresis loop areas expressed as a function of time. \dot{W}_e is the elastic energy rate and can be neglected in the case of cyclic loadings \dot{W}_S , the rate of stored energy and D_1 is the intrinsic dissipation that is proportional to self-heating.

$$\dot{W}_{def} = \dot{W}_e + \dot{W}_S + D_1 \quad (1)$$

Figure 14 illustrates the correlation between average self-heating and average hysteresis loops area during a fatigue test. In other words, it illustrates the correlation between strain energy and intrinsic

dissipation. It appears that both physical values are proportional for a wide range of test conditions: either for several load ratios and the same glass fibre orientation (a), either for the same load ratio and different glass fibre orientations. The points where the correlation has a lesser quality always correspond to short tests where temperature does not reach an equilibrium value before failure. Maximum stress level on Figure 12a illustrates such a behaviour. This satisfying proportionality may mean two different things. (i) An equivalence between W_{def} and D_1 . (ii) a constant ratio between D_1 and \dot{W}_S . Accuracy of the measurements led doesn't allow a more affirmative conclusion. When comparing this result with Figure 11, it is clear that tests led with negative load ratios on transverse or 45° specimens will show very strong self-heating since the hysteresis loops observed are very important.

Figure 14: correlation between average self-heating and average hysteresis loop area for longitudinal specimens solicited at different load ratios

In the test conditions applied (23°C/RH50%) the polyamide 6.6 matrix is very close to its glass transition. This means that a high dependency exists between temperature and overall mechanical properties. This also means that in this temperature range material ability to dissipate energy reaches a maximum. During fatigue tests characterized by strong stress amplitude and an important hysteresis loop, there is a coupling between mechanical behaviour and thermal behaviour that affects fatigue resistance. It certainly explains the curvature observed on Haigh diagram for short fatigue tests led with negative load ratios.

This kind of result illustrates that it is very difficult to fully take into account frequency effects. It is nevertheless of tremendous importance. Many lab scale characterizations are realised at low frequency, between 1Hz, and even less, and 5Hz. Most of the field tests made on full parts or assemblies are made at higher frequencies and can lead to very important self-heating. Correlations between finite elements analysis based on lab scale characterisations and part testing at significantly higher frequency might be extremely difficult if a better understanding of thermal effects is not developed.

4.2 Correlations between energetic values and fatigue resistance

Among the different energies that can characterise a fatigue test, two have been specifically followed in this study. The hysteresis loops area (see Figure 1) and the total strain energy at loading, which corresponds to the area under curve for stress as a function of strain during the loading phase of a fatigue cycle. Hysteresis loops area provides interesting correlations as shows Figure 15. All the points corresponding to one load ratio belong to a same global curve independently of glass fibres orientation, for both load ratios considered on the graph.

Total strain energy also appears as a promising way to build fatigue models. It appears even simpler than using hysteresis loops areas, because it does not require modelling of the unloading phase of fatigue cycles. Figure 16 show that for load ratios lower than $R_\sigma = 0.1$, all the points measured independently of glass fibres orientation belong to the same curve. However, for higher load ratios, it appears that the correlation is lost, and that the mechanical behaviour for a given fatigue resistance becomes significantly different, except for fatigue resistances above $3 \cdot 10^5$ cycles where independently of load ratio and glass fibre orientation, total strain energy is very well correlated with fatigue resistance.

Figure 15: correlation between fatigue resistance and hysteresis loops areas for different glass fibers orientation and two load ratios R_σ

Figure 16: correlation between fatigue resistance and total strain energy for several glass fibers orientation and load ratios

4.3 Comparison with another material tested at higher temperature

Most of the trends met at room temperature on conditioned polyamide 6.6 are linked with the proximity to glass transition of the material. When the difference $T-T_G$ increases, the phenomena observed become different. Complementary tests have been led with different conditions: $80^\circ\text{C}/\text{RH}50\%$, in a climatic chamber where both temperature and moisture are controlled to avoid any drying of the specimens during long tests. Fibres concentration was 50%, but this is believed to be a second order parameter, because at room temperature, both materials have similar fatigue and thermal behaviour. In these new conditions, self-heating is much more limited, as shows Figure 17. For a fatigue resistance of 10^4 cycles, self-heating reaches 3.5°C for longitudinal specimens reinforced with 50% glass fibres, for 10°C on a specimen tested at room temperature, RH50% reinforced with 30% of glass fibres For 45° specimens, self-heating reaches 7°C , against 14°C in the other case.

This lesser extent of thermal effects has some consequences on the preliminary Haigh diagram obtained on these materials. It is shown on Figure 18. Even for negative load ratios, lines of constant lives are not parallel, but converge. Comparison with Figure 9, or other equivalent data obtained on 90° conditioned specimens at room temperature show how much the behaviour observed are different.

Figure 17: self-heating of 50% glass fibres reinforced polyamide 6.6 (TY A218V50) with fibres oriented at 0° or 45° of applied stress, tested in fatigue at $R_\sigma=0,1$

Figure 18: preliminary Haigh diagram obtained on 50% fibre reinforced PA66 tested at 80°C, RH50%, for transverse fibres

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work focused on mean stress effects is still preliminary, though the amount of experimental data generated is already important. It emphasizes the coupling between thermal effects and mechanical resistance of the material. This coupling is especially strong when the polyamide is solicited close to its glass transition temperature T_G . Examination of Haigh diagrams shows an unusual shape in the negative load ratio domain, with lines of constant lives that remain parallel until a load ratio $R_\sigma = 0.3$.

Self-heating appears to depend strongly on load ratio and stress amplitude. As a consequence it is much more intensive for short fatigue lives and negative load ratios. Analysis led have shown that average temperature rise during fatigue tests is proportional to average hysteresis loops in a wide range of conditions. This most probably explains the unusual trends observed on Haigh diagrams.

When $|T-T_G|$ increases, thermal effects decrease, and this seems to affect strongly the shape of Haigh diagram, though results are still preliminary. It is still impossible to predict the shape of the whole diagram, but it is already clear that lines of constant lives are no longer parallel in the negative load ratio domain for the different glass fibres orientations observed.

This work will be of course completed in order to get two complete High diagrams with all the thermal and mechanical information associated. Some high resolution CT-scans are also under analysis in order to have a better understanding about damage phenomena associated with the different materials and fatigue conditions tested.

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